

IMPORTANCE OF MEDICINAL PLANTS IN HUMAN ACTIVITY

Shokirova Gavkharoy Nazirgulomovna

Doctor of Philosophy in Agricultural Sciences (PhD) Teacher,

Sarvinoz Khairulla's daughter Rasulova

is a master's student at the Department of Botany and Biotechnology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10461512>

Key words: medicinal plants, animals, tablets, complex, proteins, fats, potassium, calcium.

A unique shark folk medicine in Central Asia for centuries formed, it is based on the experience of using medicinal plants for thousands of years. The main weapon of folk medicine - medicines prepared on the basis of medicinal plants and their raw materials are counted.

It is known that it is used for the treatment of diseases in humans and animals, as well as for the prevention of these diseases plants are considered medicinal plants. People have had many medicinal plants and their uses since before Christ information about the treatment methods of diseases and they used in practice. Sumer 5000 BC written on ceramic tablets in the country and German scientists in 1956 It is also medicinal in the old writings that were managed to sleep by there was information about the methods of preparing medicinal ointments from plants. Ancient Syriac horn in Assurbanipal's library (668 BC) written in cuneiform on clay tablets 22000 tables have been found, 33 of them have medicinal plants and information about the products made on their basis is presented.

Egyptian papyri (3000 BC), ancient An example of Chinese medicine is "The Law of Roots and Roots" (from AD first written and used 2800 years ago) as ancient as we are the use of medicinal plants in the sources that have arrived and they on the basis of which methods of preparation of healing ointments are given. X.X. Kholmatov and U.A. According to Akhmedov, during the time of the ancient Greek ruler Hippocrates (460-377 BC), about 236 medicinal plants were used, which written information about him has reached us in his work "Corpus Gippokraticum". Gippocrates doctor has 3 weapons - water, plant and He used the words "Tigdir".The ancient Roman ruler Galen (130-200 AD) is also deriver provides information on 304 medicinal plants in its herbal manual.

Galen wrote almost 131 scientific works on medicine and pharmacy. Galen in medicine first prepared from the organs of plants and animals and the effect patients with the help of complex medicinal products with a powerful

effect recommended treatment. That is why such drugs are available today are also called "Galen's preparations".

The great mathematician Pythagoras was also interested in medicinal plants. Aristotle's student Theophrastus (4th century BC) is considered the "Father of Botany", his scientific work "Researches on Plants" has not lost its importance even now. One of it in the scientific works of Dioscorides (1st century BC), who was called the "father of European pharmacognosy", written several centuries ago

About 400 medicinal plants and their pictures are presented together. In his famous work "Materia medica" ancient copper

A large-scale scientific work dedicated to such excellent medicine has been widely used in medical practice by European peoples for centuries. The great scientist made ointments from several plants to increase their effect on the human body

It is suggested to use complex medicines consisting of ash

References:

1. Акашкина А.П., Российская Г.И., Лякина М.Н. Разработка и стандартизация фитопрепаратов // Актуальные проблемы создания новых лекарственных препаратов природного происхождения: Материалы II Междунар. съезда-Спб., 1998-С. 9-13.
2. Базарон Э.Г., Асеева Т.А. Вайдурья онбо - трактат индо-тибетской медицины.- Новосибирск: Наука, 1984.-116 с.
3. Балковая Е.Н. Физиолого-биохимическая характеристика эфирномасличных растений. Днепропетровск, 1958.-175с.
4. Бандюкова В.А. Применение цветных реакций для обнаружения флавоноидов путем хроматографии на бумаге // Растительные ресурсы.- 1965.-Т 4. С. 591-599.
5. Баньковский А.Д. Исследования растений, применяемых в народной медицине, на содержание алкалоидов // Труды ВИЛАР, вып. 9. М.: Медгиз, 1949,- С. 134-139.
6. Блинков И.Л. Лекарственные растения в клинике. М., 1983. - 63 с

